

SDR-Based DoA Estimation Using ESPAR Antennas with Simplified Beam Steering

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Abstract—In this paper, we have presented results of the two most popular and accurate direction-of-arrival (DoA) estimation algorithms that may be implemented in a software-defined radio (SDR) unit equipped with electronically steerable parasitic array radiator (ESPAR) antenna, in which beam steering is performed in a simple and energy-efficient way. Both algorithms rely on IQ waveform samples recorded, for different main beam directions, at the antenna output port, from which information about both amplitude and phase of an unknown signal impinging the antenna has been extracted. Measurement results indicate, that, by using SDR-based calibration setup, it is possible to perform DoA estimation with less than a single degree precision, which, according to author's knowledge, is the best result available in the literature.

Index Terms—Switched-beam antenna, electronically steerable parasitic array radiator (ESPAR) antenna, direction-of-arrival (DoA), software-defined radio (SDR), power pattern cross correlation (PPCC), multiple signal classification (MUSIC).

I. INTRODUCTION

Direction of arrival (DoA) estimation of incoming radio frequency (RF) signals is an important technique with many possible telecommunication applications, especially in future 5G systems, where localization of signal sources within an area can increase bandwidth, improve energy efficiency or will provide added values to system users [1]. The most practical approach to beamforming requires many digital signal processing (DSP) units, which, due to high systems costs and energy consumption, limit the number of applications [2].

Electronically steerable parasitic array radiator (ESPAR) antenna is an interesting concept, originally introduced in [3], in which a single active element in the center is surrounded by passive elements connected to variable reactances. Practical experiments conducted in [4] have shown that by changing reactances' values electronically it is possible to form a directional radiation pattern and also rotate it around the active element. This phenomenon can be used to direct the radiating energy towards the terminal or to find direction-of-arrival (DoA) of incoming signals using only one DSP unit [4]-[7].

Currently available algorithms for DoA estimation that can be successfully implemented in software-defined radio (SDR) equipment involve Multiple Signal Classification (MUSIC) [5], [6], estimation of signal parameters via

rotational invariant techniques (ESPRIT) [7] and Power Pattern Cross Correlation (PPCC) method [8]. Results available for ESPAR antenna with 6 passive elements connected to varactor diodes, for which bias voltages were provided from digital-to-analog converters (DAC) with 12-bit resolution, show that for a 2.484 GHz BPSK signal impinging the antenna and SNR=20 dB it is possible to estimate DoA with precision, which is the maximum absolute estimation error, equal to 2°, 3° and 7° using PPCC, MUSIC and ESPRIT methods [5]-[8]. One should note, however, that in case of PPCC algorithm only 10 snapshots of a test signal were necessary, while in case of other algorithms up to 100 snapshots were used.

An interesting concept of ESPAR antenna with simplified beam switching and 12 passive elements have been proposed for DoA estimation in wireless sensor network (WSN) applications [9], [10]. Instead of varactor diodes, single-pole, double-throw (SPDT) switches were used to connect passive elements to the ground or leave it opened. This new approach enabled steering the antenna from inexpensive and low-power microcontrollers' digital input-output (DIO) ports instead of DSP-based controller with six DAC units used previously to provide the bias voltages [8], [9], which were converted from the corresponding digital values. DoA estimation results using PPCC algorithm and testing conditions similar to those in [5]-[8] indicate, that for such ESPAR antenna, it is possible to obtain 4° precision [10], or even bring it down to 2° when SDR-based calibration setup is used [11].

In this paper, we investigate how ESPAR antenna with simplified beam steering and having 12 passive elements can be utilized for DoA estimation in SDR-based systems, which are becoming more popular due to their capability to adapt to changing environments. To this end, we have implemented two most promising algorithms available in the literature, namely PPCC, which requires only received signal strength (RSS) values recorded at the antenna output port, and MUSIC that relies on amplitude and phase of impinging signal calculated from IQ waveform samples. Measurement results show that, by careful implementation of both algorithms and using SDR-based calibration setup, it is possible to achieve more accurate DoA results using MUSIC algorithm than when PPCC method is applied.

Fig. 1. ESPAR antenna with simplified beam steering prototype proposed in [10] together with numbering of its passive elements. In the antenna, top layer metallization is the antenna's ground plane, while the SMA connector and SPDT switches are placed at the bottom (see text for explanations).

II. ESPAR ANTENNA WITH SIMPLIFIED BEAM STEERING

To be easily integrated with simple WSN nodes, ESPAR antenna design, which has been proposed in [9], [10], has a single active monopole fed by an SMA connector and is surrounded by twelve passive elements. Every passive element is connected to its SPDT switch at the bottom layer of the structure, so each element's end can be individually shortened to the ground or opened. An example of such ESPAR antenna, which were optimized to work at 2.484 GHz, fabricated using inexpensive FR4 laminate is presented in Fig. 1, while the complete design is available in [10].

If SPDT switches are connected to DIO ports of a device, ESPAR antenna radiation pattern can be associated to a corresponding steering vector $V = [v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{12}]$ stored in the device's memory. When a value v_n is set to 0, it means that n -th parasitic element is connected to the ground, while for $v_n = 1$ it is opened. It has been reported in [10], that, for five consecutive elements opened, one will obtain a directional main beam with 73.2° 3 dB beamwidth in the horizontal direction. For the antenna presented in Fig. 1 and a steering vector $V_{max}^1 = [1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]$, a directional main beam aligned with y axis (i.e. $\varphi_{max}^1 = 90^\circ$) will be created [9]. Moreover, by applying circular shift to V_{max}^1 , twelve steering vectors $\{V_{max}^1, V_{max}^2, \dots, V_{max}^{12}\}$ can be created and, in consequence, twelve radiation patterns with main beam directions $\{\varphi_{max}^1 = 90^\circ, \varphi_{max}^2 = 120^\circ, \dots, \varphi_{max}^{12} = 60^\circ\}$ can also be produced.

III. DOA ESTIMATION FOR ESPAR ANTENNAS

Among available algorithms that can be used to determine DoA of RF signals impinging ESPAR antennas [4]-[8], PPCC and MUSIC are the most promising to be used in SDR-based RF receivers. Although both algorithms require ESPAR antenna calibration, which is performed only once in an anechoic chamber before the actual DoA estimation process

starts, the key difference in their operation lies in the information required to be recorded at the antenna output port and algorithm's complexity. In case of MUSIC algorithm, the complete signal time samples have to be gathered [5] to calculate associated pseudo-spectrum using eigenvalue decomposition, while for PPCC method it is sufficient to record only receiver signal strength [8] and calculate an estimator using a simple formulae. However, if there are several uncorrelated signals impinging the antenna, MUSIC algorithm can estimate their DoA in a single analysis [6].

To implement both algorithms in a single SDR unit one has to start with ESPAR antenna calibration. To this end, one has to measure twelve ESPAR antenna's radiation patterns in the horizontal plane $\{P(V_{max}^1, \varphi), P(V_{max}^2, \varphi), \dots, P(V_{max}^{12}, \varphi)\}$ for all considered steering vectors $\{V_{max}^1, V_{max}^2, \dots, V_{max}^{12}\}$ in an anechoic chamber once with the angular step precision $\Delta\varphi$ before the actual DoA estimation. Moreover, in a practical SDR implementation, the measured patterns will be transferred to a vector form $\mathbf{p}^n = [p_1^n, p_2^n, \dots, p_I^n]^T$, in which n represents radiation pattern, while I is the number of discretized directions of the horizontal angle φ that can be gathered in a vector form as $\boldsymbol{\varphi} = [\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots, \varphi_I]^T$.

Because both algorithms rely on ESPAR antenna output signal, to maintain necessary generality, it is required that the signal is recorded and stored in the most general way. Therefore, in all further considerations, we will use the output signal written in the following form [4]-[8]:

$$y_n[k] = P(V_{max}^n, \varphi_i) s[k] + n[k] \quad (1)$$

where $y_n[k]$ are IQ signal samples recorded for n th ESPAR antenna radiation pattern $P(V_{max}^n, \varphi_i)$, $s[k]$ is a signal waveform impinging the antenna from direction φ_i and $n[k]$ is additive Gaussian noise introduced to verify DoA estimation performance for different SNR levels.

A. Power Pattern Cross-Correlation (PPCC) Method for DoA Estimation

In PPCC-based approach, to perform DoA estimation of a signal impinging the antenna, one has to calculate the highest value of a correlation coefficient calculated between measured antenna radiation patterns and the RSS measured at the antenna output port for all measured radiation patterns [8]. This operation can be written in a vector form that can be easily implemented in a SDR unit as [10]:

$$\mathbf{g} = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{12} (\mathbf{p}^n Y(V_{max}^n))}{\sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^{12} (\mathbf{p}^n \circ \mathbf{p}^n)} \sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^{12} Y(V_{max}^n)^2}} \quad (2)$$

where $Y(V_{max}^n)$ are RSS values calculated from IQ signal samples $y[k]$ recorded at the output port for ESPAR antenna radiation patterns, $\mathbf{g} = [\Gamma(\varphi_1), \Gamma(\varphi_2), \dots, \Gamma(\varphi_I)]^T$ is a vector containing discretized correlation coefficient values associated with the discretized directions in $\boldsymbol{\varphi} = [\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots, \varphi_I]^T$, and 'o' stands for the Hadamard product

(element-wise product of vectors). Then, to estimate DoA angle $\hat{\varphi}$, one has to find the value in $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$ that corresponds to the highest value within \mathbf{g} [10].

B. DoA Estimation Using MUSIC Algorithm

Multiple signal classification (MUSIC) algorithm is method that allow to obtain high resolution DoA estimation [1], [2]. It relies on two orthogonal subspaces one has to create from eigenvalue decomposition of a covariance matrix built using IQ signal samples recorded at the antenna output. Therefore, on the contrary to PPCC method, it requires both amplitude and phase information in the signal in the DoA estimation process. For the considered ESPAR antenna with simplified switching, the covariance matrix can easily be created using 12 vectors $\mathbf{y}_n = [y_n[1], y_n[2], \dots, y_n[K]]$ containing K IQ signal samples recorded at the antenna output port for all 12 ESPAR antenna radiation patterns as [6]:

$$\mathbf{R}_{yy} = \mathbf{y}\mathbf{y}^H = \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ \vdots \\ y_{12} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ \vdots \\ y_{12} \end{bmatrix}^H \quad (3)$$

where superscript H denotes Hermitian transpose and \mathbf{y} is a matrix. Using eigenvalue decomposition, one can decompose 12×12 covariance matrix \mathbf{R}_{yy} into eigenvectors and corresponding eigenvalues, which can be written in the following form:

$$\mathbf{R}_{yy}\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{V}\boldsymbol{\Lambda} \quad (4)$$

in which $\boldsymbol{\Lambda} = \text{diag}\{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_{12}\}$ is a diagonal matrix containing eigenvalues and \mathbf{V} contains the corresponding eigenvectors. Eigenvectors assigned to the lowest eigenvalues define noise subspace \mathbf{E} , while the remaining vectors correspond to the signal subspace. It means that for a single signal impinging the antenna, matrix \mathbf{E} will have 12 rows and 11 columns.

To calculate MUSIC pseudo-spectrum associated with all horizontal directions discretized in $\boldsymbol{\varphi} = [\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots, \varphi_i]^T$, one has to define a vector containing power levels measured at every angle from within $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$ for all considered steering vectors $\{V_{max}^1, V_{max}^2, \dots, V_{max}^{12}\}$, which, for a particular angle φ_i , results in 12 element vector containing a set of all measured radiation patterns $\mathbf{p}_i = [P(V_{max}^1, \varphi_i), P(V_{max}^2, \varphi_i), \dots, P(V_{max}^{12}, \varphi_i)]^T$. Then, MUSIC spectrum value at the angle φ_i for the considered ESPAR antenna with simplified beam steering becomes [6]:

$$P_{MUSIC}^{ESPAR}(\varphi_i) = \frac{1}{\mathbf{p}_i^H \mathbf{E} \mathbf{E}^H \mathbf{p}_i} \quad (5)$$

By calculating MUSIC spectrum values for all φ_i within the scope of $\boldsymbol{\varphi}$, one can easily estimate and finding the value DoA angle $\hat{\varphi}$ as a value φ_i , for which MUSIC spectrum value is the highest [6], [7].

IV. MEASUREMENTS

To verify the accuracy of both estimators we have prepared the measurement setup in our $11.9 \times 5.6 \times 6.0$ m anechoic chamber as presented in Fig. 2. The measurements were conducted using a single SDR-based Vector Signal Transceiver (NI PXIe-5840), controlled by NI PXIe-8840 PC controller and a dedicated NI LabVIEW application, following the setup proposed in [11]. During the calibration stage, we have measured all 12 radiation patterns of the ESPAR antenna at 2.484 GHz with horizontal step precision equal to $\Delta\varphi = 1^\circ$.

To examine the estimation accuracy, the same NI PXIe-5840 Vector Signal Transceiver was used to generate 2.484 GHz sinusoidal test signal impinging the antenna. The same VST was used to record RSS values and IQ waveforms for each of the 12 configurations of ESPAR antenna with a discrete angular step $\Delta\varphi_t = 1^\circ$ which resulted in 360 test directions $\varphi_t \in \{0^\circ, 1^\circ, \dots, 359^\circ\}$. 10 snapshots (with 8 IQ waveform samples per snapshot) were generated for each φ_t and the additive white Gaussian noise has been added to obtain three values of signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). Signal's directions were chosen by rotating the turntable with the receiving ESPAR antenna.

The results of PPCC and MUSIC estimation presented in Table 1 indicate that both methods provide similar results achieving precision of 1° for SNR equals to 20 dB. On the other hand, for signals with SNR equal to 5 dB, it is easy to notice that MUSIC algorithm provides better results, achieving 3° precision and RMS error equal to 0.79°, while PPCC estimated RMS error and precision was almost two times larger (consecutively, RMS = 1.33° and precision of 5°). Thus, one may notice that MUSIC algorithm is more accurate for signals with lower signal-to-noise ratio. The comparison of the results for both methods for SNR = 5 dB is presented in Fig 3.

Fig. 2. Measurement setup used in the experiment (see text for explanations)

TABLE I
DOA ESTIMATION ERRORS CALCULATED FOR VARIOUS SNR VALUES
USING CONSIDERED PPCC AND MUSIC ALGORITHMS (SEE TEXT FOR
EXPLANATIONS).

	SNR	mean	RMS	std	precision
PPCC	5 dB	1.01°	1.33°	2.79°	5°
	10 dB	0.54°	0.83°	0.97°	3°
	20 dB	0.045°	0.21°	0.045°	1°
MUSIC	5 dB	0.5°	0.79°	0.89°	3°
	10 dB	0.23°	0.48°	0.28°	2°
	20 dB	0.04°	0.2°	0.04°	1°

Fig. 3. DoA estimation error results obtained from the measurements of the (a) PPCC, (b) MUSIC algorithm for SNR=5 dB

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have verified accuracy of two most promising DoA estimation algorithms available in the literature for ESPAR antennas, namely PPCC and MUSIC, with respect to their potential applications in SDR-based systems. Based on IQ waveform samples recorded at ESPAR antenna's output port and using SDR-based calibration setup, it was possible to provide results and fairly compare them with those already published [5]-[11]. Contrary to the results produced for ESPAR antenna with 6 passive elements connected to variable varactor diodes [5]-[8], we were able to provide very accurate results for MUSIC algorithm using only 10 snapshots of recorded signal. As a consequence, we have shown that it is possible to determine DoA of signals impinging an SDR-based system equipped with ESPAR

antenna having 12 passive elements and relying on simplified beam steering with less than a single degree precision.

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